

DESIGN, CONSTRUCTION AND PERFORMANCE TEST OF A PEDAL POWERED WOOD DRILLING MACHINE

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DOI : <https://www.doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS51421>

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the Design, Construction and Performance Test of a Pedal Powered Wood Drilling Machine. It does not require any specific input energy or electric power. In this paper, human power plays a vital role. This paper consists of a larger sprocket which rotates with the help of a human-powered pedal. The smaller sprocket is connected to the plane which is mutually perpendicular to the axis of the larger sprocket and is rotated by using a chain drive. The smaller sprocket is rigidly supported utilizing shaft and bearing support. A bevel gear is set with the smaller sprocket and with that another bevel gear is set at 90 degrees with that. With that bevel gear, a larger spur gear is set with the help of a shaft and then another smaller gear is meshed with that larger spur gear. With the smaller spur gear, a drill bit will be mounted for drilling. When the pedal is operated, the drill bit is rotated which will drill the wooden block material. The main aim is to reduce the human effort for drilling various materials such as wooden blocks.

This paper's importance lies in the fact that it is green paper and helps us reduce our need for electricity too. Secondly, this cutter can be used and transferred in the working place easily. The machine can produce 477 rpm speed at drill bit. The machine drills Chambul, Kerosene, Shirish, Debdaru, and Almond wood samples. Moreover, this paper is very effective for electric power saving and rural area where there is no electricity.

Keywords: Solid Works, Computer-Aided Design (CAD.)

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, we know that, the machining operations are very important for doing engineering jobs perfectly. There are many machining operations such as drilling, grinding, cutting, sawing etc. For performing these operations perfectly, we have use different type of machines at different places, which can consume lot of time and electricity. In the rural area, electricity cut-off is a major problem which causes serious harm in work progress. Before three to four decades, when there is unavailability of electricity for working of different machines such as cutting, grinding, drilling, sawing etc. They used a manual hack saw for cutting a wood or they used an axe to cut a wood which was a very tough task for humans and consumes a very much power. But in last decades the use of an electric equipment has increased for such an operation which is also not affordable for a small industry or a domestic wood cutting purpose by poor people. The use of an electrically power wood cutting and grinding machine and drilling consumes electric power as well as cost of operation of machines much more. Then we tried to invent a machine which will be consumed less human power to perform more work [1]. Drilling is one of the most important machining operations in our engineering life. Drilling Machine is a device which is used to a material for making holes with removal of chips. There are many uses of drilling machines such as drilling, boring, countersinking, reaming, and tapping. Several types are used in metalworking: vertical drilling machines, horizontal drilling machines, center-drilling machines, gang drilling machines, multiple-spindle drilling machines, and special purpose drilling machines [2]. Now like all of materials wood is a very useful material for our life. We need to use wood in our daily life for different purposes. For using wood in those purposes, we need to drill wood object by drilling machining operation. That drilling operation is performed with a drilling machine. To run this machine, we need power. Maximum wood drilling machine is run by electric power. But the attention is to save the electric power because it is very costly and in rural area it is not available everywhere. So, we need to utilize human power to save the electricity. So human powered wood drilling machine is need to be constructed. We need to use human power to run a

manual wood drilling machine. But we need to construct such a machine that consumes less human energy to give more output. We can operate this machine by pedal. Pedal power is the transfer of energy from a human source using a foot pedal and crank system. This technology is most commonly used for transportation and has been used to propel bicycles forever a hundred years. Less commonly pedal power is used to power agricultural and hand tools and even to generate electricity. Some applications include pedal powered laptops, pedal powered grinders and pedal powered water wells. Some third world development papers currently transform used bicycles into pedal powered tools for sustainable development. This paper concentrates on pedal powered drill machining. An individual can generate four times more power by pedaling than by hand-cranking. At the rate of ¼ HP, continuous pedaling can be served for only short periods, approximately 10 minutes. However, pedaling at half this power (1/8 HP) can be sustained for close to 60 minutes but power capability can depend upon age. Because of the brainstorming exercise, it was apparent that the primary function of pedal power one specific product was particularly useful: the bicycle. Many devices can be run right away with mechanical energy [3]. We will use drill bits for performing our pedal powered wood drilling. Drill bits are a type of cutting tools used to create cylindrical holes. Bits are held in a tool called a drill chuck, which rotates them and provides torque and axial force to create the hole. Specialized bits are also available for non-cylindrical shaped holes. The shank is the part of the drill bit grasped by the chuck of a drill. The cutting edges of the drill bit are at one end, and the shank is at the other. Drill bits come in standard sizes. A comprehensive drill bit and tap size chart lists metric and imperial sized drill bits alongside the required screw tap sizes. [4] It is economically efficient machine and it helps to use for operation without any of electricity source. It will decrease unemployment and very useful in the rural area. It is very easy to use and does not require any special training to run the machine. Any person of any age can run this machine.

II. METHODOLOGY

The design, construction, and performance test of a pedal-powered wood drilling machine are the topics of this study. It doesn't need any particular electric power or input energy. Human power is a major factor in this paper. This paper has a bigger sprocket that spins with the assistance of a pedal driven by a person. Using a chain drive, the smaller sprocket is rotated in relation to the larger sprocket's axis, which is mutually perpendicular to it. Shaft and bearing support provide robust support for the smaller sprocket. The smaller sprocket is used to set a bevel gear, and another bevel gear is set at a 90-degree angle using that. Using that bevel gear, a shaft is used to set one pulley, and a belt is used to connect the two pulleys that are positioned 180 degrees apart. A drill bit will be installed on the second pulley to be used for drilling. The drill bit rotates when the pedal is pressed, drilling the wood block material. The major goal is to minimize the amount of labor required by humans to drill different materials, such wooden blocks, etc.

The machine also can be run by electric power. Importance of this paper lies in the very fact that it is green paper and helps us to reduce our electricity need too. Secondly, this cutter can be used and transferred to our working place easily. Moreover, this paper is very effective for electric power saving and rural area where there is no electricity.

Model Fabrication Techniques

The model fabrication method is controlling as the improvement system. Figure 2.1 shows the various operations of drilling machine.

Figure 2.1: Various operations on drilling machine

Types of Drilling Machine

There are different types of drilling machine we found in the world. All of those types are required for specific operations. They could be manual or automatic. Some common drilling machines are shown below.

Figure 2.2: Hand drill

Figure 2.3: Cordless drilling machine

Figure 2.4: Rotary hammer drilling machine

Figure 2.5: Radial arm drilling machine

Figure 2.6: Multi spindle drilling machine

Figure 2.7: Numerical control drilling machine

Components of Pedal Powered Wood Drilling Machine

A pedal is the part of a bicycle that the rider pushes with their foot to move the bicycle. It makes the connection between the rider's foot or shoe and the crank allowing the leg to turn the bottom bracket spindle and rotates the bicycle's wheels.

Figure 2.8: Pedal

Chain Drive Mechanism

Chain drive mechanism is a power transmission mechanism by which power is transmitted from one sprocket to another sprocket by means of chain. Here sprocket is a toothed wheel which is rotated by pedaling. Motion and power transmission from one sprocket to another means the transmission of power from one shaft to another shaft. By this process a chain drive works. Like belt and pulley, it does not slip during access power transmission. But chain drive is very noisy during operation.

Figure 2.9: Chain drive

III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Design Assumptions

The assumptions of the pedal powered wood drilling machine are-

1. The capacity of the machine to drill on a workpiece at any point which has maximum 0.1016 meters width and 0.2032 meters length and 0.0381 meters thickness.
2. The vibration of structure is as minimized as possible.
3. There is no deformation in drill bit.
4. Drill chuck of the machine has the capacity to hot the drill bit between 0.001 to 0.013 m diameter.
5. The rpm of the drill bit should be minimum 450 rpm.

Shaft Design

Here, 3 shafts are used to complete the design of the pedal powered wood drilling machine. Those are made of mild steel.

The diameter of the shafts is =16 mm

Figure 3.1: First shaft setting

Here from the figures, we can see that the first shaft is set on the metal structure by means of two bearings and between the two bearings a sprocket is set for power transmission.

Figure 3.2: Second shaft design

Here the 2nd shaft we have designed.

The height of the second shaft is = 1270 mm

It is mounted on a bearing and hold a bevel and a spur gear. The bevel gear is meshed with other bevel gear of 1st shaft.

Figure 3.3: Third shaft design

In 3rd shaft drill chuck, drill bit and smaller spur gear is mounted.

For, Shaft design calculation by taking the 1st shaft,

The shaft is 10 inches and the sprocket is set 6 inches right from the left side. The shaft is made of mild steel. And the material used most for shaft making is SAE – 1035 as rolled. So, this material is chosen for shaft design calculation.

Here the pitch circle diameter of the sprocket is = 2.56 inch

Speed of the shaft = 180 rpm

Power transmitted to the shaft = 204 watts = 0.27 hp

$$\text{Now, } hp = \frac{T N}{63000} \quad [11]$$

$$0.27 = \frac{T \times 180}{63000}$$

$$T = 94.5 \text{ lb. in}$$

$$\text{But, } T = F_b \times r \quad [11]$$

$$F_b = \frac{94.5}{1.28} = 73.82 \text{ lb}$$

$$R_{b1} = F_b \times \frac{3}{5} = 44.3 \text{ lb}$$

$$R_{b2} = F_b \times \frac{2}{5} = 29.53 \text{ lb}$$

$$M_{max} = 44.3 \times 6 = 265.8 \text{ lb.in}$$

$$M_{min} = 29.53 \times 4 = 118.12 \text{ lb.in}$$

From, AT- 7 for SAE 1035 as rolled, [11]

$$S_u = 85 \text{ ksi} , S_y = 55 \text{ ksi} , S'_n = 0.5 \times S_u = 42.5 \text{ ksi}$$

$$\text{Again, } S_n = K_L \times K_{sz} \times K_S \times K_{If} \times S'_n = 1 \times 0.85 \times 0.87 \times 1 \times 42.5 = 31.43 \text{ ksi} \quad [11]$$

$$S_{max} = \frac{M_{max} \times C}{I} = \frac{265.81 \times \frac{D}{2} \times 64}{\frac{\pi D^4}{64}} = \frac{2707.51}{D^3}$$

$$S_{min} = \frac{M_{min} \times C}{I} = \frac{1203.16}{D^3}$$

$$S_m = \frac{S_{max} + S_{min}}{2} = \frac{1.95}{D^3}; \quad S_a = \frac{S_{max} - S_{min}}{2} = \frac{0.752}{D^3}$$

Now, equivalent stress, $K_{fs} = 1.3, k_f = 1.6$ for profile keyway from AT- 13,

$$S_e = \frac{S_n}{S_y} \times S_m + K_f \times S_a = \frac{2.32}{D^3} \quad [11]$$

$$S_{es} = \frac{S_{ns}}{S_{ys}} \times S_{ms} + K_{fs} \times S_{as} \quad [11]$$

Assume $S_{as} = 0$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Here, } S_{ms} &= \frac{16 \times T}{\pi \times D^3} \quad [11] \\ &= \frac{0.48}{D^3} \end{aligned}$$

$$S_{ns} = \frac{S_n}{\sqrt{3}} = 18.15 \text{ ksi} \quad [11]$$

$$S_{ys} = \frac{S_y}{\sqrt{3}} = 31.75 \text{ ksi} \quad [11]$$

$$S_{es} = \frac{18.15}{31.75} \times \frac{0.48}{D^3} = \frac{0.27}{D^3}$$

$$\text{Now, } \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2 = \left[\left(\frac{S_e}{S_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{S_{es}}{S_{ns}}\right)^2\right] \quad [11]$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{1.5}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{2.31799}{D^3 \times 31.43}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{0.27}{D^3 \times 18.15}\right)^2$$

$$D = 0.52 \text{ inch}$$

So, the minimum diameter of the shaft is 0.52 inch. A shaft of 0.63 inches diameter is used in the machine. $0.52 < 0.63$. So, shaft design is ok.

Surface Base Design

The surface base on which the full structure will be built is made of wood.

The length of the base = 1220 mm

The width of the base = 558 mm

The thickness of the base = 45 mm

Figure 3.4: Surface base

On that base, a seat is mounted with 3 side support. The seat is also made of wood. Wood is used for structure because it is very low cost and can give any required shape very fast.

The height of the seat from the base = 610 mm

Figure 3.5: Seat

Bearing Design

In this machine total 6 bearings are used. Those bearings are used for smooth machining operation and to

reduce friction. By means of bearing the shafts are perfectly set and the power transmission is very easy.

The diameter of the bearings = 15 mm

Figure 3.6: Design of bearing

For bearing design calculation,

Assume according to [11], Radial Reaction, $F_x = 470 \text{ lb}$

Thrust, $F_z = 350 \text{ lb}$

In this bearing outer ring stationary, smooth load service 2 hour/day service

Total service hour = 17000 hour

Maximum shaft rotation = 500 rpm

Now, for ball bearing = $\frac{F_z}{C_r \times F_x}$ and rotation factor, $c_r = 1$, for outer ring stationary. [11]

$$\text{Here, } \frac{F_z}{C_r \times F_x} = \frac{350}{1 \times 470} = 0.744$$

$$\text{Now, let, } \frac{F_z}{C_r \times F_x} > Q$$

Then, $F_e = 0.56c_r F_x + c_t F_z$ [11]

$$= (0.56 \times 1 \times 470) + (1.8 \times 350) = 893.2$$

$$B_{10} = 17000 \times \frac{60}{1} \times 500 = 510 \times 10^6 \text{ rev [11]}$$

$$F_r = (B_{10})^{\frac{1}{3}} \times F_e \text{ [11]}$$

$$= 11^{\frac{1}{3}} \times 382$$

$$= 849.56$$

From table 12.3 [11]

For close value of F_r Bearing Number will be 308

$$F_s = 5020 \text{ lb}$$

$$F_r = 7040 \text{ lb}$$

For, 308 number bearing balls number = 8 from table 12.3 [11]

$$\text{Inside diameter} = \frac{19}{32} \text{ inch} = 0.594 \text{ inch} = 15.08 \text{ mm} \approx 15 \text{ mm}$$

And a bearing of 15 mm inner diameter has used for the design. So, design is ok.

Chain and Sprocket Mechanism

Here 2 sprockets are used for power transmission. One is larger sprocket and the other is smaller sprocket. Those are connected together by a chain. Pedal is set with the larger sprocket for power giving. By rotating the pedal, the larger sprocket will rotate and for that smaller sprocket will also rotate.

Number of teeth in larger sprocket, $t_1 = 48$

Number of teeth in smaller sprocket, $t_2 = 16$

Diameter of the larger sprocket, $D_1 = 194 \text{ mm}$

Diameter of the smaller sprocket, $D_2 = 65 \text{ mm}$

Here the chain and sprocket are connected together for the transmission of power.

The diameter of the larger sprocket, $D_1 = 194 \text{ mm}$

$$\text{The pitch of the chain, } P = D_1 \times \sin\left(\frac{180}{t_1}\right) \text{ [11]}$$

= 0.5 inch

By the pitch 0.5 inch from table 17.8 [11]

The chain is 40 number

Average ultimate strength = 3700 lb.

Limiting speed = 2300 fpm

Chain length = Number of links × Pitch

Here, We got Pitch, $P = 0.5 \text{ inch}$

Now, Number of links, = 112 [Measured]

Now, Chain Length= 112×0.5

= 56 inch

Figure 3.7: Chain and sprocket

Final CAD Model

Figure 3.8: Final CAD mode

Construction

For construction, metal and wood were used. The structure had been made of wood and the support also been made of wood. The two sprockets are stand on a metal structure and support. After setting the larger sprocket on the metal angle rod which is 8 inch long. Then the shaft with bearing and smaller sprocket were set on the metal structure of angle rod which length is 2 feet. Then some bearing bushings had been made to set the bearing on wood structure by wire nail and screw. 3 shafts were used for sprocket, gear and bearing setting. Sprocket, bearing, gear is set on shaft by bushings. Two different size of drill bit to drill on wood. Rack and pinion mechanism was used on worktable for upward and downward movement for drilling operation. Nuts and bolts were used for clamping the workpiece on the worktable. The two-bevel gear were used, one had 10 teeth and the other had 18 teeth. Two spur gear were used, one had 105 teeth and the other had 22 teeth. The drill chuck was used can hold 1mm to 13mm drill bit. And two different sizes of drill bit were used, one was 7.14mm diameter and the other was 6.35 mm diameter. Then finally the construction was finished successfully.

Fully Constructed Paper

After all the calculations and manual process, the final paper is developed based on the design.

Figure 3.9: Constructed Paper

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Performance Test

- Measurement of Speed (rpm)**

Number of teeth of Larger Sprocket, $t_1 = 48$

Number of teeth of Smaller Sprocket, $t_2 = 16$

Average rpm is given on Larger Sprocket, $N_1 = 60$ rpm (measured)

The rpm transmitted to smaller sprocket, N_2 ,

$$\frac{t_1}{t_2} = \frac{N_2}{N_1}$$

$$N_2 = \frac{48}{16} \times 60$$

$$= 180 \text{ rpm}$$

Speed of smaller sprocket = Speed of smaller bevel gear

Number of teeth of 1st bevel gear, $t_3 = 10$

Number of teeth of 2nd bevel gear, $t_4 = 18$

Speed transmitted to 2nd bevel gear, N_4 ,

$$\frac{t_3}{t_4} = \frac{N_4}{N_3}$$

$$N_4 = 100 \text{ rpm}$$

Speed of larger 2nd bevel gear = Speed of Larger spur gear

Number of teeth of larger spur gear, $t_5 = 105$

Number of teeth of smaller spur gear, $t_6 = 22$

Speed transmitted to the smaller spur gear, N_6 ,

$$\frac{t_5}{t_6} = \frac{N_6}{N_5}$$

$$\frac{105}{22} = \frac{N_6}{100}$$

$$N_6 = 477.3 \text{ rpm} \approx 477 \text{ rpm}$$

The rpm of the drill bit will be, $N_6 = 477 \text{ rpm}$

- Measurement of Torque**

The average power to weight ratio during pedaling by an average man is = 3 [7][8]

The weight of my body is = 68 kg

Then the power I should produce during pedaling is = $68 \times 3 = 204$ watts

The average power given by an average man during pedaling is = 200 to 300 watts [9]

So, let us assume power of pedaling is, $P = 204$ watts

$$\text{Now the Torque} = \frac{P}{\omega} = \frac{P \times 60}{2\pi N}$$

$$\text{Torque in larger sprocket} = \frac{204 \times 60}{2 \times 3.1416 \times 60} = 32.47 \text{ N.m}$$

$$\text{Torque in smaller sprocket} = \frac{204 \times 60}{2 \times 3.1416 \times 180} = 10.82 \text{ N.m}$$

Torque in smaller sprocket = Torque in 1st bevel gear

$$\text{Torque in 2nd bevel gear} = \frac{204 \times 60}{2 \times 3.1416 \times 100} = 19.48 \text{ N.m}$$

Torque in 2nd bevel gear = Torque in Larger spur gear

$$\text{Torque in smaller spur gear} = \frac{204 \times 60}{2 \times 3.1416 \times 477} = 4.08 \text{ N.m}$$

Now the Torque in Drill Bit will be = 4.08 Nm.

• **Measurement of Cutting Speed and Depth of Cut**

Cutting Speed of a Drill Bit, $v = \frac{\pi DN}{1000}$ [10]

For D = 6.35 mm Drill Bit,

$$\text{Cutting speed will be} = \frac{3.1416 \times 6.35 \times 477}{1000}$$

=9.52 m/min

$$\text{Depth of Cut} = \frac{D}{2} = \frac{6.35}{2} = 3.175 \text{ mm}$$

For D = 7.14 mm Drill Bit,

$$\text{Cutting Speed will be} = \frac{3.1416 \times 7.14 \times 477}{1000}$$

= 10.7 m/min

$$\text{Depth of Cut} = \frac{D}{2} = \frac{7.14}{2} = 3.57 \text{ mm}$$

V. RESULTS

Table 5.1: For D = 7.14 mm Drill Bit drilling time

Wood Sample	Thickness (inch)	Time (second)
Chambul	0.75	27
Kerosene	0.75	17
Shirish	0.75	11
Debdaru	0.75	19
Almond Wood	0.75	07

Table 5.2: For D = 6.35 mm Drill Bit drilling time

Wood Sample	Thickness (inch)	Time (second)
Chambul	0.75	45
Kerosene	0.75	24
Shirish	0.75	21
Debdaru	0.75	27
Almond Wood	0.75	12

VI. DISCUSSION

From the performance test of pedal powered wood drilling machine, the rpm of the drill bit was 477 rpm and the torque was 4.08 Nm. and that is enough for drilling soft wood. It would be a little time consuming for hard wood. And the cutting speed of 6.35 mm diameter drill bit was 9.52 m/min and 7.14 mm diameter drill bit were 10.7 m/min. In the result 5 wood sample were used of same thickness and it could drill 8 inch long and 4-inch width wood piece at any point. Here Chambul wood piece took longest time 27 seconds with 7.14mm drill bit and Almond wood takes shortest time to drill 7 seconds. Because chambul was the hardest wood among the sample wood used. So, it took more time than other sample wood. Debdaru took 19 seconds, kerosene took 17 seconds, Shirish took 11 seconds to drill with 7.14 mm drill bit. But there was little vibration in drill bit due to slight misalignment of gear and shaft. Without that issue the machine was good enough to operate and drill wood piece.

VII. CONCLUSION

The pedal powered wood drilling machine was constructed according to the design. All the objectives of this paper are fulfilled. The performance was very well for drilling wood piece. This machine was suitable for the village area and the area also where electricity cut off problem occurs. Because this machine did not require any

electric power. It required human power for running. No special training was needed to run this machine. Any people could run this machine. A very good exercise would also be done during running this machine. And this was very cheap compared to another automated machine.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Almighty for His kindness upon us without which it would be impossible to finish this paper. We would like to pay our sincere gratitude to Prof. Dr. Mihir Ranjan Halder Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET) for his guidance, support and concern throughout this paper. We are indebted to him. We express our cordial gratefulness to Dr. Kazi Afzalur Rahman, Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Chittagong University of Engineering Technology (CUET), Dr. Sobahan Mia, Professor and Head, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET), colleagues, for providing a great opportunity to enhance presentation and study-based skills which will later help flourishing in different sectors. We would like to thanks all the staffs of workshops and labs of Department of Mechanical Engineering, CUET & KUET, especially Machine Shop, Fluid Mechanics Lab for their cooperation at many stages.

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